

1 **Appendix A**

2 A detailed search strategy for a narrative review on *Sporothrix brasiliensis* (cat-transmitted
3 sporotrichosis) to include international literature written in English, Spanish, and Portuguese. The
4 initial search criteria included literature published since 2008, but newly published literature was
5 included throughout the writing of this manuscript and the references and citations were mined for
6 additional pertinent literature. Publication bias was minimized through the inclusion of multiple
7 databases in our search strategy.

8

9 **Search Strategy:**

10

Sporothrix brasiliensis

Database	Strategy	Run Date	Records
Medline (Ovid) 1946-	(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR s brasiliensis OR rose thorn disease* OR rose gardener disease OR rose gardeners disease* OR rose handler disease* OR rose handlers disease* OR esporotricos*).mp. OR exp Sporothrix/ OR exp Sporotrichosis/ AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses).mp. Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-	4/18/19	179 articles
Embase (Ovid) 1947-	((sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR s brasiliensis OR rose thorn disease* OR rose gardener disease OR rose gardeners disease* OR rose handler disease* OR rose handlers disease* OR esporotricos*).mp. OR exp Sporothrix/ OR exp sporotrichosis/ AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses).mp.) OR exp Sporothrix brasiliensis/ Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-	4/18/19	270 articles -164 duplicates =106 articles
CAB Abstracts (Ovid) 1910-	(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR s brasiliensis OR rose thorn disease* OR rose gardener disease OR rose gardeners disease* OR rose handler disease* OR rose handlers disease* OR esporotricos*).mp. OR exp Sporothrix/ OR exp sporotrichosis/ AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses).mp. Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-	4/18/19	209 articles -141 duplicates =68 articles
Global Health (Ovid)	(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR s brasiliensis OR rose thorn disease* OR rose	4/18/19	148 articles

1910-	gardener disease OR rose gardeners disease* OR rose handler disease* OR rose handlers disease* OR esporotricos*).mp. OR exp Sporothrix/ OR exp sporotrichosis/ AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses).mp. Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-		-148 duplicates =0 articles
Cochrane Library	#1(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR "s brasiliensis" OR "rose thorn disease" OR "rose gardener disease" OR "rose gardeners disease" OR "rose handler disease" OR "rose handlers disease" OR esporotricos*):ti,ab,kwLimits 17 #2MeSH descriptor: [Sporothrix] explode all treesMeSH 2 #3MeSH descriptor: [Sporotrichosis] explode all trees MeSH 9 #4(brasiliensis OR brasilienses):ti,ab,kwLimits 13 #5#1 OR #2 OR #3 Limits 17 #6#4 AND #5 Limits 0 Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-	4/18/19	0 articles -0 duplicates =0 articles
Scopus 1960-	TITLE-ABS-KEY (sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR "s brasiliensis" OR "rose thorn disease" OR "rose gardener disease" OR "rose gardeners disease" OR "rose handler disease" OR "rose handlers disease" OR esporotricos*) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(brasiliensis OR brasilienses) AND (LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2019) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2018) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2017) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2016) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2015) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2014) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2013) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2012) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2011) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2010) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2009) OR LIMIT-TO (PUBYEAR , 2008)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "Spanish") OR LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "Portuguese"))	4/18/19	317 articles -268 duplicates =49 articles
Academic Search Complete (Ebsco)	TI,AB(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR "s brasiliensis" OR "rose thorn disease" OR "rose gardener disease" OR "rose gardeners disease" OR "rose handler disease" OR "rose handlers disease" OR esporotricos*) OR DE "SPOROTRICHOSIS" OR DE "SPOROTRICHUM" AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses)	4/18/19	120 articles -110 duplicates =10 articles

	Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-, peer-reviewed		
CINAHL (Ebsco)	TI,AB (sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR "s brasiliensis" OR "rose thorn disease" OR "rose gardener disease" OR "rose gardeners disease" OR "rose handler disease" OR "rose handlers disease" OR esporotricos*) OR (MH "Sporotrichosis") AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses) Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-, peer-reviewed	4/18/19	9 articles -9 duplicates =0 articles
GreenFILE (Ebsco)	TI,AB(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR "s brasiliensis" OR "rose thorn disease" OR "rose gardener disease" OR "rose gardeners disease" OR "rose handler disease" OR "rose handlers disease" OR esporotricos*) AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses) Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-, peer-reviewed	4/18/19	3 articles -3 duplicates =0 articles
Agricultural & Environmental Science Collection (Proquest) 1960-	TI,AB(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR "s brasiliensis" OR "rose thorn disease" OR "rose gardener disease" OR "rose gardeners disease" OR "rose handler disease" OR "rose handlers disease" OR esporotricos*) OR MAINSUBJECT.EXACT("Sporotrichosis") AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses) Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-, peer-reviewed	4/19/19	203 articles -160 duplicates =43 articles
ProQuest Central (Proquest) 1960-	TI,AB(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR "s brasiliensis" OR "rose thorn disease" OR "rose gardener disease" OR "rose gardeners disease" OR "rose handler disease" OR "rose handlers disease" OR esporotricos*) OR MESH.EXACT("Sporotrichosis") OR MESH.EXACT("Sporothrix") AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses) Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-, peer-reviewed	4/19/19	165 articles -130 duplicates =35 articles
Virtual Health Library (WHO)	(tw:(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR "s brasiliensis" OR "rose thorn disease" OR "rose gardener disease" OR "rose gardeners disease" OR "rose handler disease" OR "rose handlers disease" OR esporotricos*)) AND (tw:(brasiliensis OR brasilienses))	4/19/19	237 articles -208 duplicates =28 articles

	Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-		
CDC Stacks	Title,Subject,Description(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR "s brasiliensis" OR "rose thorn disease" OR "rose gardener disease" OR "rose gardeners disease" OR "rose handler disease" OR "rose handlers disease" OR esporotricos*) AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses) Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-	4/19/19	0 articles
Homeland Security Digital Library	Title,Subject,Description(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR "s brasiliensis" OR "rose thorn disease" OR "rose gardener disease" OR "rose gardeners disease" OR "rose handler disease" OR "rose handlers disease" OR esporotricos*) AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses) Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-	4/19/19	0 articles
PubMedCentral (NLM)	TI,AB(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR "s brasiliensis" OR "rose thorn disease" OR "rose gardener disease" OR "rose gardeners disease" OR "rose handler disease" OR "rose handlers disease" OR esporotricos*) OR "sporothrix"[MeSH Terms] OR "sporotrichosis"[MeSH Terms] AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses) Exclude: Medline Limits: English, Spanish, Portuguese, 2008-	4/19/19	65 articles -40 duplicates =25 articles
InFocus Conference and Inform II Conference (ISHAM)	(sporothrix* OR sporothrices OR sporotrichum* OR sporotrichos* OR "s brasiliensis" OR "rose thorn disease" OR "rose gardener disease" OR "rose gardeners disease" OR "rose handler disease" OR "rose handlers disease" OR esporotricos*) AND (brasiliensis OR brasilienses)	4/19/19	3 articles -0 duplicates =3 articles
		De-duplicated in EndNote:	546 articles

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Notes: Duplicates were identified using EndNote automated “find duplicates” function with preference set to match on title, author, and year.

16 **Appendix B**

17 **Therapeutic regimens and other recommendations for feline sporotrichosis**

18 The drug of choice and therapeutic dosage for treating feline sporotrichosis may vary with the
 19 clinical severity of the case (general health conditions, number and location of lesions, and presence
 20 of extracutaneous signs). Table B1 details the common therapeutic options.

21 **Table B1: Doses of itraconazole monotherapy or combination therapy with potassium iodide recommended**
 22 **in cases of feline sporotrichosis.**

23

Drug	Dose	Indications for use
ITZ monotherapy (capsule)	Cats $\geq 3\text{kg}$: 100 mg/cat/day Cats $\geq 1\text{kg}$ – 3kg : 50 mg/cat/day Cats $< 1\text{kg}$: 25 mg/kg/day	-Cats with fixed cutaneous lesions and naïve to antifungal therapy
ITZ plus KI (capsules)	ITZ: same doses described above KI: 2.5-20 mg/kg/day - Half the dose of KI in the first week of treatment	-Cats presenting multiple skin lesions, mucosal lesions, or presence of respiratory signs -Cases refractory to ITZ monotherapy

24

ITZ: Itraconazole; KI: Potassium iodide.

25

26 Routes of administration:

27 Itraconazole and potassium iodide capsules can be opened and mixed with wet cat food for ease of
 28 administration [1,2]. This will also decrease contact with the sick cat and risk of zoonotic
 29 transmission of *S. brasiliensis*.

30 Criterion for cure and duration of therapy:

31 In feline sporotrichosis, the criterion for cure is clinical, with the disappearance of all the clinical
 32 signs [3]. Antifungal therapy may range from a few weeks to many months (median time = 4 – 9
 33 months), and the infected cat should remain isolated from other animals throughout the duration of
 34 treatment [4–6].

35 The treatment should be maintained for one month after the clinical cure. In cats presenting lesions
 36 (cutaneous and/or mucosal) on the nasal region and/or respiratory signs, it is recommended to
 37 maintain the therapy for two months after the clinical cure to minimize the risk of recurrence.

38 Use of compounded itraconazole and potassium iodide:

39 A study comparing different forms of itraconazole (brand name, generic pelletized, and
40 compounded from bulk powder) found that compounded itraconazole should be avoided, but
41 generic itraconazole appears to serve as a reasonable alternative to brand name itraconazole [7].
42 Another study found that the pharmacokinetic data for generic formulation itraconazole were
43 similar enough that therapeutic concentrations could be achieved. Compounded itraconazole
44 produced low plasma concentrations, so it is unlikely to be effective [8]. Unlike itraconazole, KI
45 should be compounded in capsules for therapy [1].

46 Adverse reactions and contraindications:

47 Due to the occurrence of clinical and/or laboratory adverse reactions (nausea, anorexia, vomiting,
48 increased serum liver enzymes), temporary drug suspension may be necessary, until the appetite
49 returns and/or enzymes return to reference levels. Thus, it is recommended to monitor the clinical
50 and laboratory parameters (mainly serum liver enzymes) [2]. Oral silymarin (30mg/kg/day) or
51 S-adenosylmethionine (SAME) (20 mg/kg/day) should be administered for cats with clinical adverse
52 reactions or elevated transaminase levels [9,10].

53 The use of immunosuppressive drugs, like glucocorticoids, is contraindicated. Any concurrent
54 bacterial infection should be simultaneously treated [11].

55 The effectiveness of topical antifungal treatment alone has not been evaluated, therefore it is not
56 recommended. Also, due to the closer contact when manipulating the sick cat, the risk of zoonotic
57 transmission is increased.

58

59 **2.2. Other therapeutic options**

60 Amphotericin B:

61 Intralesional or subcutaneous amphotericin B, in conjunction with oral itraconazole, is an alternative
62 for cases refractory to itraconazole monotherapy [3,12,13].

63 Liposomal amphotericin B in combination with itraconazole was successfully described in only one
64 case of feline sporotrichosis refractory to itraconazole [3]. However, the high cost of this formulation
65 limits its use [2].

66 Ketoconazole:

67 Clinical studies on the use of ketoconazole for the treatment of feline sporotrichosis have shown
68 varied results [5,6,14–19]. However, itraconazole has replaced ketoconazole due to its greater
69 effectiveness and safety [6,20].

70 Terbinafine:

71 The effectiveness and safety of terbinafine for the treatment of human sporotrichosis has been
72 confirmed, but its therapeutic potential in animal sporotrichosis is not yet established [21,22]. Two
73 cases of canine sporotrichosis caused by *S. brasiliensis* were successfully treated with this drug [23].

74 Fluconazole:

75 Fluconazole showed low activity against *S. brasiliensis* recovered from cats with sporotrichosis [24].
76 Even so, this drug is recommended for lymphocutaneous sporotrichosis in humans when the patient
77 cannot tolerate other agents [25]. However, there are few reports of the use of this drug in feline
78 sporotrichosis [5,26], and its effectiveness and safety is not known.

79 Posaconazole:

80 Posaconazole has shown good activity *in vitro* against *S. brasiliensis* isolates; however, there are no
81 studies evaluating the effectiveness and safety of this drug in feline sporotrichosis [27]. In a cat
82 infected by *S. pallida*, the clinical cure was achieved with itraconazole and subsequent posaconazole
83 [28]. As in the case of liposomal amphotericin B, the high cost may limit its use.

84 Other alternative therapies:

85 Thermotherapy [29], adjunctive surgical treatment [29,30], and cryosurgery [31], with or without
86 concurrent itraconazole, are other options for the treatment of feline sporotrichosis. The use of these
87 therapeutic alternatives should be carefully evaluated on a case-by-case basis.

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